

ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

8 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ ПРАВОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 8, НОМЕР 4

JOURNAL OF LAW RESEARCH

VOLUME 8, ISSUE 4

ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ПРАВОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF LAW RESEARCH

№4 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9130-2023-4>

Бош муҳаррир:
Главный редактор:
Chief Editor:

Abdurasulova Qumriniso Raimqulovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Fayziev Shoxrud Farmonovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)

ТАҲРИРИЙ МАСЛАҲАТ КЕНГАШИ | РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ | EDITORIAL BOARD

12.00.01 - ДАВЛАТ ВА ҲУҚУҚ НАЗАРИЯСИ ВА ТАРИХИ. ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАЪЛИМОТЛАР ТАРИХИ / ТЕОРИЯ ПРАВА И ГОСУДАРСТВА, ИСТОРИЯ ПРАВОВЫХ УЧЕНИЙ / THEORY OF LAW AND STATE, HISTORY OF LEGAL DOCTRINES

Boboyev Halimboy Boboyevich

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Ahmedshaeva Mavlyuda Axatovna

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Muxitdinova Firyuza Abdurashidovna

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Adilxodjayeva Surayyo Maxkamovna

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Sattorov Abdug'affor

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Artur Gambaryan

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Armaniston)

Yosuke Shamoto

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Yaponiya)

12.00.02 - КОНСТИТУЦИОННЫЙ ҲУҚУҚ, МАЪМУРИЙ ҲУҚУҚ, МОЛИЯ ВА БОЖХОНА ҲУҚУҚИ / КОНСТИТУЦИОННОЕ ПРАВО; АДМИНИСТРАТИВНОЕ ПРАВО; ФИНАНСОВОЕ ПРАВО / CONSTITUTIONAL LAW; ADMINISTRATIVE LAW; FINANCIAL RIGHT

Malikova Gulchexra

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Xusanov Ozod Tillabayevich

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Selimanova Svetlana Mixaylovna

yuridik fanlar doktori (O'zbekiston)

Xvan Leonid Borisovich

yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)

Peshkova Xristina Vyacheslovovna

yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (Rossiya)

Sung Un Lee

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Janubiy Koreya)

12.00.03 - ФУҚАРОЛИК ҲУҚУҚИ. ТАДБИРКОРЛИК ҲУҚУҚИ. ОИЛА ҲУҚУҚИ. ХАЛҚАРО ХУСУСИЙ ҲУҚУҚ / ГРАЖДАНСКОЕ ПРАВО; ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЕ ПРАВО; СЕМЕЙНОЕ ПРАВО; МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЕ ЧАСТНОЕ ПРАВО / CIVIL LAW; BUSINESS LAW; FAMILY LAW; PRIVATE INTERNATIONAL LAW

Oqyulov Omonboy

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Ro'zinazarov Shuhrat Nuraliyevich

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Ruziyev Rustam Jabborovich

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Borotov Mirodiljon Xomudjonovich

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Toshev Boboqul Norqobilovich

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Shomuxamedova Zamira Shoislamovna

yuridik fanlar doktori, (O'zbekiston)

Ahmad Issa Altweissi

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Iordaniya)

12.00.04 - ФУҚАРОЛИК ПРОЦЕССУАЛ ҲУҚУҚИ. ХЎЖАЛИК ПРОЦЕССУАЛ ҲУҚУҚИ. ҲАҚАМЛИК ЖАРАЁНИ ВА МЕДИАЦИЯ / ГРАЖДАНСКОЕ ПРОЦЕССУАЛЬНОЕ ПРАВО; ХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОЕ ПРОЦЕССУАЛЬНОЕ ПРАВО; АРБИТРАЖНЫЙ ПРОЦЕСС И МЕДИАЦИЯ / CIVIL PROCEDURE LAW; ECONOMIC PROCEDURAL LAW; ARBITRATION PROCESS AND MEDIATION

Esanova Zamira Normurodovna

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Mamasidiqov Muzaffar Musajonovich

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Jason A.

Kanton Federal sud markazi (AQSH)

12.00.05 - МЕҲНАТ ҲУҚУҚИ. ИЖТИМОИЙ ТАЪМИНОТ ҲУҚУҚИ / ТРУДОВОЕ ПРАВО; ПРАВО СОЦИАЛЬНОГО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ / THE LABOR LAW; SOCIAL SECURITY LAW

Usmanova Muborak Akmalxanovna

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Gasanov Mixail Yuriyevich

yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)

Sattorova Gulnoza Djurakulovna

yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)

Murodova Gulnora

yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)

Denisov Gleb

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)

Fayziyev Shuxrat Xasanovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Usmonov Muhammadi Bahridinovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Xolmuminov Juma
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Jo'rayev Yuldash Achilovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Skripnikov Nikolay Kuzmich
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)

Po'latov Baxtiyor Xalilovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Salomov Baxrom Salomovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Salayev Nodirbek Saparbayevich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Osmonaliev Qayrat
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Aleksey Kibalnik
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Kudryavtsev Vladislav Leonidovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Sergey Shoshin
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (Rossiya)
James B.
Eaglin Federal sud markazi (AQSH)

Rustambayev Mirzayusup Hakimovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Zufarov Rustam Axmedovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Kabulov Rustam
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Rajabova Mavjuda Abdullayevna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Taxirov Farxod
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Ismailov Isomiddin
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Hamidov Nurmuhammad Orif o'g'li
yuridik fanlar bo'yicha falsafa doktori (O'zbekiston)
Yuldoshev Rifat Raxmadjonovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Tojikiston)
Djansarayeva Rima Ernatovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Yelena Antonyan Aleksandrovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Matthew Light
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Kanada)

Inog'omjonova Zumratxon Fatxullayevna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Pulatov Yuriy Safiyevich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
To'laganova Gulchehra Zaxitovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Muxiddinov Faxriddin Muxiddinovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Mirzov Davron Miragzamovich
yuridik fanlar doktori (O'zbekiston)
Rijakov Aleksandr Petrovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)

Stoyko Nikolay Genadyevich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Iskandarov Zayniddin
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Tojikiston)
Sergey Pen
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Aleksey Purs
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (Belarus)
Jurgen Maurer
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Germaniya)
Kevin Curtin
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (AQSH)

Ismoilov Bahodir Islamovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Matkarimova Gulchehra Abdusamatovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Yuldasheva Govxerjan
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Alexander Trunk
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Germaniya)

1. Худайбердиева Азиза Нормухамедовна КОНСТИТУЦИОННО-ПРАВОВЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ИНСТИТУТОВ ГРАЖДАНСКОГО ОБЩЕСТВА СОГЛАСНО ПРОЕКТУ КОНСТИТУЦИИ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН В НОВОЙ РЕДАКЦИИ.....	5
2. Артиков Дилмурод Рахматиллаевич МАЪМУРИЙ ОРГАНЛАР ҚАРОРЛАРИ ВА ҲАРАКАТЛАРИ (ҲАРАКАТСИЗЛИГИ) УСТИДАН МАЪМУРИЙ СУДЛАРГА МУРОЖААТ ҚИЛИШ САБАБЛАРИ ВА МУАММОЛАРИ.....	12
3. Ergashev Ikrom Abdurasulovich THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE PROMOTION OF SYSTEM OF TAX CULTURE.....	20
4. Нариманов Бекзод Абдувалиевич ПАРЛАМЕНТ НАЗОРАТИ ИНСТИТУТИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШДА ФУҚАРОЛИК ЖАМИЯТИ ИНСТИТУТЛАРИ ИШТИРОКИНИ КЕНГАЙТИРИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ.....	26
5. Юлдашева Феруза Улугбековна ЯНГИ ТАҲРИРДАГИ КОНСТИТУЦИЯДА ФУҚАРОЛАР ДАВЛАТ ХИЗМАТИГА КИРИШДА ТЕНГЛИГИ КАФОЛАТЛАНМОҚДА.....	34
6. Khursanov Rustam Kholmurodovich THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN CONCLUDING CONTRACTS FOR THE PROVISION OF TELECOMMUNICATIONS SERVICES.....	41
7. Тагаева Гузал Кучкаровна КОММЕРЧЕСКАЯ ТАЙНА КАК РАЗНОВИДНОСТЬ КОНФИДЕНЦИАЛЬНОЙ ИНФОРМАЦИИ.....	48
8. Tojiboyev Akbar Zafar o'g'li AYIRBOSHLANADIGAN QARZ (CONVERTIBLE DEBT/NOTE) SHARTNOMASI MONIYATI: STARTAPLAR MISOLIDA.....	56
9. Тошбоева Робия Собировна КАДАСТРОВАЯ ИНФОРМАЦИЯ О ПРИРОДНЫХ РЕСУРСОВ КАК ОСОБЫЙ ОБЪЕКТ «УМНОГО» (SMART REGULATION) “ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНОГО” ПРАВОВОГО РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ.....	63
10. Арашов Музаффар Хакимбой ўғли ОММАВИЙ ТАРТИБСИЗЛИКЛАР ВА БИР ГУРУҲ ШАХСЛАРНИНГ БЕЗОРИЛИГИНИ ФАРҚЛАШНИНГ ТУРЛИ МАСАЛАЛАРИ.....	71
11. Исломов Бунёд Очилович МЕКСИКА ҚЎШМА ШТАТЛАРИ ЖИНОЯТ ҚОНУНЧИЛИГИДА ЖАЗОНИ ЕНГИЛЛАШТИРИШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ.....	80
12. Исмоилов Шоҳаббос Ғайратжон ўғли РАҚОБАТЧИНИ ОБРЎСИЗЛАНТИРИШ ИНСОФСИЗ РАҚОБАТНИНГ ТУРИ СИФАТИДА.....	87

12.00.03-ГРАЖДАНСКОЕ ПРАВО. ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЕ ПРАВО. СЕМЕЙНОЕ ПРАВО. МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЕ ЧАСТНОЕ ПРАВО

Khursanov Rustam Kholmurodovich,
Tashkent State University of Law,
Doctor of Philosophy in Law,
Associate Professor
E-mail: hursanov.rustam75@gmail.com

THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN CONCLUDING CONTRACTS FOR THE PROVISION OF TELECOMMUNICATIONS SERVICES

For citation: Khursanov Rustam Kholmurodovich. THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN CONCLUDING CONTRACTS FOR THE PROVISION OF TELECOMMUNICATIONS SERVICES. Journal of Law Research. 2023, 8 vol., issue 4, pp.41-47

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8025395>

ANNOTATION

This article explores the potential benefits and challenges of using artificial intelligence (AI) in the process of concluding contracts for telecommunications services. The author argues that AI can streamline the contracting process by automating routine tasks, reducing errors, and providing personalized recommendations based on customer data. However, the article also highlights potential legal and ethical concerns related to the use of AI in contract negotiations, such as transparency, accountability, and bias. Overall, this article provides valuable insights into how AI can transform the telecommunications industry while raising important questions about its implementation and regulation.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, telecommunications services, contract conclusion, digital transformation, automation, machine learning, contract management, customer experience, efficiency, innovation.

Хурсанов Рустам Холмуродович,
Тошкент давлат юридик университети
кафедра доценти, юридик фанлар номзоди
E-mail: hursanov.rustam75@gmail.com

**ТЕЛЕКОМУНИКАЦИЯ ХИЗМАТЛАРИНИ КЎРСАТИШ БЎЙИЧА
ШАРТНОМАЛАРНИ ТУТИШДА СУЊИЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада телекоммуникация шартномаларини тузиш жараёнида сунъий интеллектдан (СИ) фойдаланиш мумкин бўлган афзалликлар ва муаммолар қиёсий таҳлил қилинган. Шунингдек, мақолада сунъий интеллект орқали одатий вазифаларни автоматлаштириш, хатоларни камайтириш ва миждозлар маълумотлари асосида шахсий тавсиялар бериш орқали шартнома тузиш жараёнини соддалаштириши мумкинлиги таҳлил қилинган. Шу билан бирга, мақолада, шартнома тузишда сунъий интеллектдан фойдаланиш билан боғлиқ бўлиши мумкин бўлган ҳуқуқий муаммолар, масалан, шаффофлик, жавобгарлик ва тарафларнинг тенглиги каби масалалар ўрганилган. Умуман олганда, ушбу мақола сунъий интеллект телекоммуникация саноатини қандай ўзгартириши ва уни амалга ошириш ва тартибга солиш бўйича муҳим саволларни кўтариши ҳақида қимматли маълумотларни тақдим этади.

Калит сўзлар: сунъий интеллект, телекоммуникац, телекоммуникация хизматлари, шартнома, шартномалар тузиш, рақамли трансформация, автоматлаштириш, самарадорлик, инновация.

Хурсанов Рустам Холмуродович,
Ташкентский государственный
юридический университет
кандидат юридических наук, доцент
E-mail: hursanov.rustam75@gmail.com

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА ПРИ ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИИ ДОГОВОРОВ НА ОКАЗАНИЕ ТЕЛЕКОММУНИКАЦИОННЫХ УСЛУГ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье исследуются потенциальные преимущества и проблемы использования искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) в процессе заключения договоров на телекоммуникационные услуги. Автор утверждает, что ИИ может упростить процесс заключения контрактов, автоматизируя рутинные задачи, уменьшая количество ошибок и предоставляя персонализированные рекомендации на основе данных о клиентах. Однако в статье также освещаются потенциальные юридические и этические проблемы, связанные с использованием ИИ в переговорах по контрактам, такие как прозрачность, подотчетность и предвзятость. В целом, эта статья дает ценную информацию о том, как ИИ может преобразовать телекоммуникационную отрасль, поднимая при этом важные вопросы о его внедрении и регулировании.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, телекоммуникационные услуги, заключение договоров, цифровая трансформация, автоматизация, машинное обучение, управление договорами, клиентский опыт, эффективность, инновации.

The telecommunications industry has undergone significant changes over the past few years, with the widespread adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) being one of the most notable developments. AI has been used to improve various aspects of telecommunications services, from customer service to network management. One area where AI is having a significant impact is in the conclusion of contracts for the provision of telecommunications services.

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) in concluding contracts has been a controversial topic in recent years. AI has the potential to revolutionize the way contracts are negotiated, drafted, and executed. However, there are concerns about the reliability and fairness of AI-powered contract systems.

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) in concluding contracts is a rapidly growing trend in the business world. AI has the potential to revolutionize the way contracts are negotiated, drafted, and executed. With the ability to analyze large amounts of data and make predictions based on that data, AI can play a critical role in streamlining the contracting process.

One of the main benefits of using AI in contract conclusion is its ability to automate repetitive tasks. For example, AI can be used to review and compare multiple versions of a contract, identifying any inconsistencies or errors that may have been missed by human reviewers. This can save time and reduce errors in the drafting process.

AI technologies such as machine learning and natural language processing have made it possible for telecom companies to streamline the contract conclusion process. These technologies can analyze large amounts of data and identify patterns that are relevant to the contract conclusion process. For instance, they can identify common clauses and terms that are often included in contracts, which can then be used to create standardized contract templates.

The use of AI in contract conclusion has several advantages, including increased efficiency, accuracy, and cost-effectiveness. AI can automate many of the tasks involved in contract conclusion, such as drafting and reviewing contracts, identifying potential legal issues and risks, and negotiating terms with customers.

In addition, AI-powered chatbots have made it possible for telecom companies to interact with customers in a more efficient manner. These chatbots can answer common questions related to contract conclusion and provide customers with relevant information about the services being offered. They can also help customers navigate through complex contracts by summarizing key provisions or highlighting important clauses.

One example of how AI is used in contract conclusion is through the use of chatbots. Chatbots are computer programs that use natural language processing (NLP) to interact with customers in a conversational manner. They can provide customers with information about available telecommunications services, answer questions about plans and pricing, and even help customers select plans that best meet their needs.

Contract negotiation is a complex process that involves multiple parties with different interests and goals. AI can help streamline this process by analyzing data from previous negotiations and identifying patterns and trends that can be used to optimize future negotiations. This can result in faster, more efficient negotiations that save time and money for all parties involved.

Once a contract is negotiated, AI can also assist with drafting the agreement itself. By analyzing the terms of the negotiation, as well as relevant legal precedents and regulations, AI can generate a draft contract that is tailored to the specific needs of all parties involved. This can save time and reduce errors that might result from manual drafting.

However, there are concerns about the reliability of AI-powered contract systems. Critics argue that these systems may not be able to account for all possible scenarios or nuances in negotiations, leading to incomplete or inaccurate contracts. Additionally, there are concerns about bias in AI algorithms that could lead to unfair or discriminatory contract terms.

To address these concerns, it is important to develop transparent and accountable AI systems for contract negotiation and drafting. This includes ensuring that algorithms are regularly audited for accuracy and fairness, as well as providing clear explanations of how decisions are made by these systems.

Moreover, AI technologies have made it possible for telecom companies to personalize their contracts based on customer data. By analyzing data such as usage patterns and customer preferences, AI algorithms can suggest customized contract terms that are more likely to be accepted by customers.

Chatbots can also be used to draft contracts for telecommunications services based on customer preferences and requirements. By analyzing data from previous contracts and customer interactions, chatbots can generate customized contracts that meet specific customer needs while also ensuring compliance with legal requirements.

Another advantage of using AI in contract conclusion is its ability to analyze data from past contracts and identify patterns or trends. This can help businesses make more informed decisions about future contracts, such as which terms are most likely to be successful or which clauses may need to be renegotiated.

However, there are also potential drawbacks to using AI in contract conclusion. One concern is that relying too heavily on technology could lead to a loss of human judgment and intuition. For

example, an AI system may not fully understand the nuances of a particular industry or market, leading it to make suboptimal decisions.

Additionally, there are concerns around data privacy and security when using AI systems to manage sensitive information such as contracts. Businesses must ensure that their systems are secure and compliant with relevant regulations such as GDPR.

Despite the benefits of using AI in concluding contracts for telecommunications services, there are also potential risks that must be considered. For example, there is a risk that AI algorithms may not always make accurate decisions or may be biased towards certain groups of customers. Additionally, there is a risk that customer privacy may be compromised if personal data is used without proper consent or security measures.

Another way that AI is used in contract conclusion for telecommunications services is through document analysis. By using machine learning algorithms to analyze large volumes of data from previous contracts and other sources, AI can identify patterns and trends that could be useful in drafting new contracts.

Document analysis can also be used to review existing contracts for potential legal issues or risks. For example, AI can identify clauses that may conflict with current laws or regulations or may expose the company to financial or reputational risks.

Accordingly, there was a need for specialists who, having professional knowledge, would help to conclude contracts, draw them up properly, and in the event of conflict situations, defend the rights and interests of specific individuals. These circumstances served as one of the reasons for the formation of the legal profession, and also necessitated the accumulation and storage of relevant information [1].

The indicated consequences of improper performance of the obligation are not aimed at forcing the contractor to properly perform the work contract, but at reducing the customer's losses and restoring the balance property interests of the parties. As correctly noted in the literature, "the main goal of applying a reduction in the cost of work is not so much to impose an additional property burden on the contractor for the violation, but to restore the equivalence of commodity-money relations [2].

Artificial intelligence is becoming more and more relevant today with the rapid development of the IT industry. The creation of programs that independently perform mental actions without human intervention and, accordingly, the creation of a specific result, gives rise to its own legal problems. "Artificiality" in artificial intelligence is represented by the fact that the owner of the mind is not a person, but some kind of inanimate device. After all, the mind is a feeling that is inherent only to a person, and the program created by him can perform actions at a certain level of the human mind. In this case, every action of a normal person is based on a certain mind and thinking, and artificial intelligence creates a unique legal consequence, being able to repeat the mental action of this person.

The use of artificial intelligence when concluding contracts for the provision of telecommunications services is carried out directly through the software. Such a customer enters into an agreement with artificial intelligence by filling in the standard terms of the agreement on the website of the corresponding operator. In this case, artificial intelligence enters into an agreement with the client on behalf of the operator. In other words, artificial intelligence selects the conditions that make up the content of the contract with the client, confirms its conclusion, starts providing telecommunications services to the client, determines the subject of the contract, determines the price of the services provided, and other such contracts.

In the field of telecommunications, contracts concluded with the help of artificial intelligence are manifested in such actions as presenting to customers the types of services offered by operators and providers, familiarizing them with the content of the contract, choosing an Internet service package that is acceptable to them. client. These services are provided with the help of artificial intelligence. In these cases, the concept of representation can also be applied to the involvement of artificial intelligence technologies in the relationship between the provider and consumer of telecommunications services.

One of the functions of civil law is to regulate public relations in such a way as to guarantee the stability of civil circulation and the construction of civil law relations on the basis of equality, discretion, autonomy of will and property independence.

Recognition of the possibility of a commensurate reduction in the contract price has the purpose of both regulation and protection of contractual relations between the parties. This the method of protection, on the one hand, determines the customer's guarantees for payment exactly the value of the result of the work that he received, on the other hand, protects the contractor from unjust enrichment of the customer. The use of this method of protection allows you to save the legal relations of the parties, ensuring a balance of their property rights and obligations, fair economic interests and expectations [3].

Improving the quality of telecommunication services is another important aspect of ensuring consumer satisfaction. Service providers must invest in technology and infrastructure to ensure that their services are reliable, fast, and accessible. They must also provide adequate customer support to address any issues that may arise, and must continually evaluate and improve their services to meet changing consumer needs.

In the contract for the provision of services using “artificial intelligence”, technologies “artificial intelligence” it is necessary to include a condition on the basis for granting by the service provider, the right to use these results of intellectual activity. If the performer has purchased exclusive right under an agreement on the alienation of an exclusive right or the right to use these objects on the basis of a license agreement, it is expedient in an agreement on provision of services, include a condition on details these contracts. If the performer has the right to use “artificial intelligence”, technologies of “artificial intelligence” on the basis of a license agreement in a service agreement using these objects, you must include an assurance that the license agreement has not expired. Compliance with this assurance reality, it is advisable to provide forfeit [4].

For a contract for the provision of services the right holder for the introduction of “artificial intelligence”, technologies of “artificial intelligence” in the activities of the user, the content of the license agreement is of great importance. In the text of this contract for the provision of services, it is necessary to make link to the license agreement, or you can use the license agreement as appendices to such an agreement.

Services for the introduction of “artificial intelligence”, technologies of “artificial intelligence” in the user's activities can be provided not only by the copyright holder, but also by a third person whose identity must be agreed between the user and the copyright holder.

In this case, a license agreement must be concluded between the copyright holder and a third party on the use of “artificial intelligence”, “artificial intelligence” technologies by this person in order to implement them in user activity. In the relevant contract for the provision of services between the user and the third party must contain a link to this license agreement.

As you know, property or non-property benefits are recognized as objects of civil rights. In philosophy, "good" is a relative concept, since this or that thing is not good in itself, but only in a certain respect, when it benefits the subject. In this regard, not any object obtained as a result of the use of digital technologies can be attributed to the objects of civil rights, but only one that has value, real or potential. It should be particularly noted that the very name "digital asset" contains an indication of the property value of a digital object.

The use of tokens and cryptocurrencies in the financial sphere already indicates that these objects have a certain value. The fact that a token or a new cryptocurrency may not meet the expectations of investors and turn out to be a soap bubble has no legal significance. They have at least a potential value. This remark is also true for big data, domain names and virtual gaming property.

But the question of the property value of accounts deserves special attention, since recently it has been actively discussed in connection with inheritance problems.

An account is an account that is created for the user when registering in an electronic system [5]. This is a set of data about a user stored in a computer system, necessary for his identification (authentication) and providing access to his personal data and settings. To use an account (i.e. to log in under someone's name), you usually need to enter a username and password. Users can perceive

an account as a personal page, profile, cabinet, a place to store personal and other information on a certain Internet resource[6].

Previously, accounts on social networks and in virtual games were not subject to direct transfer either in the order of singular or in the order of universal succession.

Examples of legislative regulation of this sphere can be found in the legislation of some states of America. The Delaware State in August 2014 was the first to legislatively provide for the possibility of registering ownership of Internet accounts belonging to a deceased citizen [7]. In Idaho and Oklahoma, relatives of the deceased can access blogs, mail and social pages, and in Indiana — to documents and information stored electronically (or get a copy of them) [8].

The specifics of a digital asset can be called its existence in a kind of environment of trust between anonymous counterparties, which (trust) is formed based on the use of algorithms [9]. A kind of trust in the algorithm in an untrusted environment determines the peculiarities of the turnover of digital assets.

In practice, many services explicitly prohibit the transfer of accounts without the explicit consent of the company. For example, the Steam Subscriber Agreement states that the account and all information on it is purely personal and cannot be sold or transferred as a legacy to third parties without Valve's consent [10]. At the same time, large funds are invested in the profile. As a result, all the subscriber's attachments in the event of his death are burned without the possibility of transferring them to someone else in the order of inheritance.

It is also important to note that German doctrine does not allow the transfer of access to the page without a prior user request [11]. It is noted that the rights transferred by inheritance are not of a proprietary nature, but are an obligation to maintain a personal account. This, in turn, can have an extremely negative impact on the inherited property, access to which is lost. In this regard, there are polar positions in judicial practice.

In conclusion, the use of artificial intelligence in concluding contracts for telecommunications services has revolutionized the industry by increasing efficiency and improving customer experience. However, it is important that companies use these technologies responsibly and with an eye towards potential risks and ethical considerations. By doing so, they can continue to reap the benefits of AI while maintaining customer trust and loyalty.

Overall, the use of artificial intelligence in concluding contracts for the provision of telecommunications services offers several benefits for both providers and customers. Providers benefit from increased efficiency and accuracy in contract drafting and negotiation processes while customers benefit from more personalized and customized contracts that meet their needs. As AI continues to evolve, it is likely that its use in the telecommunications industry will become even more prevalent and will continue to enhance the quality of services provided to customers.

While there are both benefits and challenges associated with using artificial intelligence in concluding contracts, it is clear that this technology has significant potential for improving efficiency and accuracy in this area. As businesses continue to adopt AI solutions for various functions within their organizations, it is likely that we will see increasing use of this technology in contract negotiation and execution.

In conclusion, the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in concluding contracts has become increasingly popular due to its ability to streamline the contract negotiation process and reduce errors. AI can review large amounts of data and provide insights that would be difficult for humans to identify. Additionally, AI can help parties identify potential risks and inconsistencies in contracts, which can ultimately lead to more efficient and effective negotiations.

While there is great potential for AI to revolutionize the way contracts are negotiated and drafted, it is important to proceed with caution. By developing transparent and accountable AI systems for contract conclusion, we can ensure that these technologies are used responsibly to benefit all parties involved.

However, the use of AI in contract negotiation raises important questions about legal liability and accountability. As AI continues to evolve and become more sophisticated, it is essential for lawmakers to establish clear guidelines and regulations regarding the use of AI in legal transactions.

Overall, the use of AI in concluding contracts has the potential to revolutionize the way contracts are negotiated and executed. While there are still challenges that need to be addressed, it is clear that AI will continue to play an important role in the future of contract law.

References/Иқтибослар/Сноски:

1. Sinelnikova V. N. Transformation of Contract Law in Conditions of Using Self-Organized Programs Ex jure. 2018. № 4. Pp. 108–117. (In Russ.). DOI: 10.17072/2619-0648-2018-4-108-117.
2. Karapetov A. G. Means of protecting the rights of the creditor in the light of the reform of civil legislation // Bulletin of Civil Law. 2009. No. 4. S. 182.
3. Ibragimova S. V. Commensurate Price Reduction under the Contract. Ex jure. 2019. № 4. Pp. 65–75. (In Russ.). DOI: 10.17072/2619-0648-2019-4-65-75.
4. Poduzova E. B. Contracts for the provision of services in the field of the use of "artificial intelligence" and technologies of "artificial intelligence": problems of theory and practice // Actual problems Russian law. - 2022. - Т. 17. - No. 8. - S. 59–67. — DOI: 10.17803/1994-1471.2022.141.8.059-067.
5. The newest explanatory dictionary of the Russian language of the XXI century: approx. 1,500 words / Comp. E.N. Shagalova. M., 2011. pp. 24-25.
6. Dictionary of business terms.URL: <https://dic.academic.ru/dic.nsf/business/17471>; https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Account_recording; <https://ru.wiktionary.org/wiki/аккаунт> (date of application: 17.09.2018).
7. Lienko S. What happens to accounts on the Internet after the death of the owner // Cossa.ru . 2015. March 17. URL: <https://www.cossa.ru/152/98997> (date of application: 05.09.2018).
8. Yurga V. Is it possible to inherit an account on Facebook or VKontakte? // <url>. 2015. March 14. URL: https://zakon.ru/discussion/2015/4/13/mozhno_li_peredat_po_nasledstvu_akkaunt_v_facebook_ili_vkontakte (date of application: 05.09.2018).
9. Sannikova L.V., Kharitonova Yu.S. Legal aspects of the application of distributed registry technology for the formation of a new environment of trust in society // Civil Law. 2018. № 5. URL: https://store.steampowered.com/subscriber_agreement/russian/#1.
10. Kartashov M.A. Inheritance of a personal page on a social network after the death of a user in the judicial practice of Germany. Part one // The Law.<url> [Electronic resource] URL: https://zakon.ru/blog/2018/05/24/nasledovanie_lichnoj_stranicy_v_socialnoj_seti_posle_smerti_polzovatelya.
11. Rakhmonov, Otabek. "Features of improving the reorganization of corporate law entities in the Republic of Uzbekistan." Евразийский журнал академических исследований 3, no. 2 Part 4 (2023): 213-216.
12. Otabek, R. (2022). Foreign experience in reconstruction of corporate law. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(8), 538-542.

ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

8 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ ПРАВОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 8, НОМЕР 4

JOURNAL OF LAW RESEARCH

VOLUME 8, ISSUE 4

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Тадқиқот город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000